

EFFECTS OF EXPERIENTIAL AND INQUIRY TEACHING STRATEGIES ON UPPER BASIC STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN SOCIAL STUDIES

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Abstract

The research was on the effects of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies on upper basic students' achievement in social studies in Education Zone C, Benue State. The study adopted a pretest, posttest, control group, quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Social Studies Achievement Test (SOSAT) with the reliability value of 0.82 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21). The target population of this study was 7689 which was the population of Upper Basic Education II Social Studies students in the study area. A sample of 252 students drawn from 6 schools within 3 Local Government Areas (LGA) out of 9 LGA in the zone selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that students taught Social Studies using experiential strategy had significantly higher mean achievement scores than those taught using discussion method [$F=589.014$, $P(0.0001 < 0.05)$] and students taught Social Studies using inquiry strategy had significantly higher mean achievement scores than

those taught using discussion method [F=220.321, P(0.0001<0.05)]. There was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using experiential and inquiry teaching strategies [F=5.900, P(0.198>0.05)]. It was recommended among others that since experiential and inquiry teaching strategies was found to be an effective method for improving students' achievement in Social Studies; Social Studies teacher's trainee should be trained on the use of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies and serving teachers should be encouraged to use it.

Key words: Experiential, inquiry, students' achievement, Social Studies.

INTRODUCTION

Social Studies is the study of man as he interacts with his/her different environments. The environment could be physical, social, political, educational, cultural or economic. There is virtually no sphere in human endeavour that social studies does not touch. Akoh (2010) pointed out that Social Studies involves the totality of man as it takes and uses concepts, ideals, skills, knowledge, values and attitude from the social science subjects such as economics, geography, psychology among others. The emergence of Social Studies education into the Nigerian school curriculum was part of a general culture and values in response to the problems of neglect of societal culture and values (Igu, 2009). The author posits that Social Studies was seen as a necessary and veritable tool after the civil war to help rebuild the battled nation and to reverse colonial education which did not appreciate and accommodate our cherished culture and values. The author further opine that social studies have not achieve its aims due to ineffective instructional methods, teachers related factors and schools related factors among others. Social Studies as an integrated discipline, has been equipped with necessary vital tools for promoting and sustaining culture and values in the society (Mbata & Omabe, 2010).

The importance of Social Studies lies in its ability to foster the acquisition and development of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that are worthwhile through appropriate teaching/learning methods in order to meet challenges in Nigeria (Mbata & Omabe, 2010). In this regard, Mbata and Omabe (2010) observes that repositioning Social Studies will help it to achieve its ultimate goal which is to produce the right calibre of students equipped with the right type of culture, values, attitudes and skills for national development. Adesua (2013) notes that any educational process that trains children without Social Studies will fail to provide all round development of the individuals, because Social Studies is a great force behind individual personality, moral and societal development. Therefore, any nation

that isolates or neglect Social Studies education stands the risk of becoming morally and socially bankrupt.

Despite the importance of Social Studies education and the efforts of researchers to improve on its teaching and learning, achievement of students in the subject remains low in Nigeria. This situation of fluctuation in achievement of students in Social Studies has affected the moral, social harmony and education pursuits and aborted the ambition of many candidates that aspired to study studies in higher institutions. If Social Studies is properly taught using effective and appropriate strategies, Social Studies could arouse students' interest and provide the nation with valuable development, which are required for the achievement of both personal and national goals.

Social Studies teachers should not stick or focus on only a particular method of teaching for every lesson. This is because it is only when a student has good mastery of the subject that he/she can do well in examination. Okafor (2008) in a related contribution laments that the teaching and learning of Social Studies in Nigerian schools is faced with serious problems and challenges. Some of these problems include among other things, lack of incentives for teachers, dearth of instructional materials, inadequate qualified teachers and non-utilization of effective teaching strategies.

The attention of many Social Studies educators has continued to be directed at searching for an appropriate method of teaching. Many Social Studies education researchers have focused on teaching methods such as field trip techniques, project method, lecture, discussion method among others. Ajiboye (2007) also notes that discussion method is still popular in Nigeria, despite its limitations. The author stressed that discussion method has received a lot of criticism from different researchers. It is said to be teacher-centered as it does not involve learners' active participation. This according to the author has led to the failure of the students in Social

Studies in external examinations such as Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE). Teachers should note that Social Studies encompass prior and concrete experiences and active participations of the learners to improve the learning outcome. In this regard, for Social Studies instruction to be effective, teachers should employ innovative teaching strategies such as experiential and inquiry teaching strategies.

Experiential teaching strategy emphasizes that learners should construct their own knowledge by testing ideas based on prior knowledge and experience, and applying these ideas to a new situation and integrating the new knowledge gained with pre-existing intellectual constructs (Ayuba, 2012). The author added that knowledge construction is based on personal experiences and the continual testing of hypotheses. Experiential teaching strategy is a form of strategy that encourages thoughtful reflection on experience (Ajayi, 2018). Ali (2010) described experiential teaching strategy as a strategy whereby students are engaged in direct experience and focused reflection in order to increase knowledge, develop skills, and clarify values.

Experiential learning as the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming experience. Kolb (1984) explained experiential teaching model portrays four major stages involved in the learning process. These consist of two related modes of grasping experiences. These are concrete experience and abstract conceptualization. It also consists of another two major models of transforming experiences. These are reflective observation and active experimentation. These stages may or may not follow in sequence. It depends on the nature of learning that is to take place. The experiential teaching model makes room for transfer of learning to take place. This is seriously lacking in the current discussion teaching method used by teachers.

Experiential teaching strategy begins with an experience that the students have had, followed by an opportunity to reflect on that experience. Then students may conceptualize and draw conclusions about what they

experienced and observed. This leads to future actions in which the students experiment with different behaviors. According to Andresen (2008), for a learning process to be truly experiential, the following attributes are necessary: the goal of experience-based learning should involve something personally significant or meaningful to the students; Students should be personally engaged. Reflective thought and opportunities for students to write or discuss their experiences should be ongoing throughout the process. The whole person is involved, meaning not just their intellect but also their senses, their feelings and their personalities. Students should be recognized for prior learning they bring into the process.

Canella (2009) notes that students' construct their own meaning by building on their previous knowledge and experience. New ideas and experiences are matched against existing knowledge and the learner constructs new or adapts rules to make sense of the world. In such an environment, the teacher cannot be in charge of the students' learning, since everyone's view of reality will be so different and student will come to learning already possessing their own constructs of the world. Teaching styles based on experiential strategy therefore mark a conscious effort to move from those traditional, objectivist didactic models, memory-oriented transmission models to a more student-centred strategy.

Ayuba (2010) describes inquiry teaching strategy, as a strategy where concepts are demonstrated as fixed facts from where students are required to draw inferences either through questions drawn by the teacher or from their own direct observation. The author adds that the investigator formulates his own problem, he then designs his own activity or procedures for collecting data or relevant information and he arrives at his own conclusion and subsequent principles involved. The author further adds that inquiry-based learning tasks stimulate curiosity in the students, encouraging them to actively explore and seek out new evidence. According to Frishberg (2011), inquiry teaching strategy is a strategy to teaching that relies on student-centred activities and questioning rather than traditional teacher-centered strategy which

relies on textbooks and lectures. The author buttresses that the teacher's role is more of a mentor than authority as such well-crafted problems and minimal amount of information is what the students are presented with leading them to discover the answers which bring them to their own understanding of the ideas required. In an inquiry-based learning environment, students should be engaged in activities that help them actively pose questions, investigate, solve problems, and draw conclusions about the world around them. It is on this note that this study sets out to investigate the effect of innovative strategies such as experiential and inquiry teaching strategy on students' achievement in Social Studies among Upper Basic students in Zone C of Benue State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies on upper basic students' achievement in Social Studies. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determined the effect of experiential teaching strategy on students' achievement in Social Studies.
2. Ascertained the effect of inquiry teaching strategy on students' achievement in Social Studies.
3. Ascertained the difference between the effect of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies on students' achievement in Social Studies

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using inquiry teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method?
3. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students

taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using inquiry teaching strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using inquiry teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using inquiry teaching strategy.

Research Design and Procedure

The study used pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design. The study area was zone C of Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 7,689 UBEII students in the 122 approved Upper Basic Education schools. 252 students were purposively sampled from 6 schools, two schools each in Oju, Otukpo and Ohimini Local Government Areas of Benue state. During lessons, the teachers used as research assistant taught the experimental group 1 social studies topics using experiential lesson notes and the experimental group 2 were taught using inquiry lesson notes while the control group was taught the same Social Studies topics using the discussion lesson notes. An instrument known as Social Studies Achievement Test (SOSAT) developed by the researchers and validated by three experts from Social Studies and one other from measurement and evaluation all from Benue State University, Makurdi was used to collect the data. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument before it was used. The SOSAT, a 30 item multiple choice instruments yielded reliability

coefficients of 0.82 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula.

Result and Table

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and null hypotheses

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method?

Table 1: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Social Studies using Experiential Strategy and Discussion Method

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	σ	$\bar{x}$	σ	
Experiential	84	11.64	1.28	26.10	1.76	14.46
Discussion	86	11.59	1.24	17.31	2.13	5.72
Mean difference		0.05		8.79		8.74

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1. The results in Table 1 reveal that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 8.74 in favour of students in experiential strategy group. This implies that students taught using experiential

teaching strategy achieved higher than their discussion group counterparts.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using inquiry teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method?

Table 2: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Social Studies using Inquiry Strategy and Discussion Method

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	σ	$\bar{x}$	σ	
Inquiry	82	11.60	1.26	24.77	1.62	13.17
Discussion	86	11.59	1.24	17.31	2.13	5.72
Mean difference		0.01		7.46		7.45

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The answer to research question two is contained in Table 2. The results in Table 2 reveal that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 7.45 in favour of students in inquiry strategy group. This implies that students taught using inquiry teaching

strategy achieved higher than their discussion group counterparts.

Research Question Three

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using inquiry teaching strategy?

Table 3: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Social Studies Using Experiential Strategy and Inquiry Strategy

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Experiential	84	11.64	1.28	26.10	1.76	14.46
Inquiry	82	11.60	1.26	24.77	1.62	13.17
Mean difference		0.04		1.33		1.29

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The answer to research question three is contained in Table 3. The results in Table 3 reveal that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 1.29 in favour of students in experiential strategy group. This implies that students taught using experiential

teaching strategy achieved slightly higher than their inquiry group counterparts.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Table 4: ANCOVA Test for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Social Studies using Experiential Strategy and Discussion Method.

Source	Type III sum of square	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	19810.130a	2	512.011	175.001	.000
Intercept	1512.020	1	1512.020	470.081	.000
Pre-test	213.015	1	213.015	72.080	.000
Method	1930.101	1	1930.101	589.014	.000
Error	770.101	167	5.111		
Total	111199.001	170			
Corrected Total	2822.291	169			

a. R squared = .014 (Adjusted R Squared= .069)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

ANCOVA result in Table 4 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores between experiential and discussion method of teaching in favour of experiential teaching strategy [F(1,169) =589.014, P(0.0001<0.05)]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that experiential teaching strategy is significantly more effective than discussion

method in achievement of students in Social Studies.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Social Studies using inquiry teaching strategy and those taught using conventional discussion method.

Table 5: ANCOVA Test for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Social Studies using Inquiry Strategy and Discussion Method

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	4608.059a	2	822.130	284.040	.000
Intercept	1994.101	1	1994.101	448.002	.000
Pre-test	278.089	1	278.089	91.001	.000
Method	2030.031	1	2030.031	220.321	.000
Error	911.054	165	21.110		
Total	593010.000	168			
Corrected Total	2329.100	167			

a. R squared = .220 (Adjusted R Squared= .211)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

ANCOVA result in Table 5 reveals that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores between the students taught Social Studies using inquiry and those taught using discussion method in favour of inquiry teaching strategy [$F(1,167) = 220.321$, $P(0.0001 < 0.05)$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that inquiry teaching strategy is significantly more effective than discussion method in achievement of students in Social Studies.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy and those taught using inquiry teaching strategy.

Table 6: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Social Studies using Experiential Strategy and Inquiry Strategy

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	3010.010a	2	554.111	205.008	.000
Intercept	1730.015	1	1730.015	493.081	.000
Pre-test	334.010	1	334.010	98.806	.000
Method	52.110	1	52.110	5.900	.198
Error	759.000	163	21.111		
Total	43030.000	166			
Corrected Total	372.070	165			

a. R squared = .625 (Adjusted R Squared= .613)

ANCOVA Tests in Table 6 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement of students taught Social Studies using experiential and those taught using inquiry strategy [$F(1,165) = 5.900$, $P(0.198 > 0.050)$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that both experiential and inquiry teaching strategies enhanced students' achievement in Social Studies.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed that students taught Social Studies using experiential teaching strategy achieved significantly higher than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This finding agrees with Adewale (2012) and Aliu (2014) who found that students achieved higher when exposed to experiential teaching strategy than their counterparts that were exposed to traditional method in economics and history respectively. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that experiential strategy helped the learner to possess a meaningful in-depth knowledge of the content area when compared to the discussion method. Experiential teaching strategy is said to involve engagement in real world experiences where learners are actively engage in testing their prior experience to give answers to new situation unlike discussion method. This finding disagrees with Oyeyemi (2011) who found that experiential approach has no significant difference in achievement of students when compare with field trip method in History

It was also found that students exposed to inquiry have higher achievement than their counterpart that was exposed to discussion method. This finding agrees with Haruna (2012) who found that students have higher achievement when they are actively engaged in solving problems through inquiry than when they become passive learners as obtained in the use of traditional method. The likely explanation for this outcome may also be connected to the fact that the use of inquiry teaching strategy orients students towards

searching for solutions to the problems themselves when compared to the discussion method. Another major finding in this study was that students exposed to experiential teaching achieved slightly higher than those exposed to inquiry strategy but ANCOVA test shows that the difference was not significant. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that experiential strategy helped the learner to possess a meaningful in-depth knowledge of the content area and the use of inquiry teaching strategy orients students towards searching for solutions to the problems themselves.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies could enhance student achievement in Social Studies. If experiential and inquiry teaching strategies proposed by this study are adopted in social studies teaching and learning it will likely boost the achievement of students.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made from the findings;

- i. Social Studies teacher's trainee should be train on the application of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies to enhance greater achievement.
- ii. Serving teachers should employ the use of experiential and inquiry teaching strategies in teaching to enhance students' achievement in Social Studies.
- iii. Workshops, conferences and seminars should be organized by Ministry of Education and other school administrators on the need for experiential and inquiry teaching strategies in the teaching of Social Studies in order to enhance students' achievement.

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